

ANTHROPOLOGICAL INQUIRY OF ECONOMIC BENEFITS OF BURIAL PRACTICES AMONG IBIL PEOPLE IN OGOJA, CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

Anthropology is the holistic study of humans and their cultures within their societies. The celebration of those who have passed away is a deeply rooted cultural practice within the Ibil Ogoja Community in Cross River State. The deceased are honoured with great reverence, as they are believed to maintain a special bond with the living. This research explored the economic benefits of the burial practices in the Ibil Ogoja community. The study was based on Structural Functionalism Theory. An ethnographic research design was utilised, incorporating in-depth interviews, focus group discussions, and observational methods for data collection. Participants were chosen through purposive sampling for the research. An interview guide served as the tool for data collection. Thematic analysis was performed to interpret the narratives shared by the participants, to address the research questions. The results revealed that the burial celebrations among the Ibil Ogoja people have led to the thriving of several craft and profession and the opportunities for meaningful economic engagements in the area, and the social environment that characterize burial event provide conducive atmosphere for generating revenue among the Ibil Ogoja people of Cross River State. The study concludes that celebrations of the dead through burial ceremony contributes to the prosperous nature of many businesses and arts with the opportunities for meaningful economic engagements in the area. Therefore, it is recommended the elders should harmonise the burial rituals for economic benefits of the people and community in the celebration of the dead among the Ibil people in Ogoja, Cross River State.

Keywords: Anthropology, Economics benefits, Burial, Celebration of the dead, and Ibil Ogoja people

Introduction

Culture exists within all human communities across the globe. It is nearly inconceivable to imagine a society devoid of culture, as the interactions among individuals are shaped by a framework of learned behaviours and belief systems (Nabila, 2009). From the functionalist theoretical perspective, cultural traits or practices that endure are those that fulfil functions contributing to societal stability. In this context, culture is regarded as a means to satisfy needs and a tool for developing solutions to challenges faced by individuals while defining their roles (Schiffman and Kaun, 2010). Nevertheless, cultural traits differ from one society to another. In light of this variation, Idang (2015) posited that the unique traits and characteristics of a specific group set them apart from other groups within the human family.

Throughout human history, culture has provided individuals with meaning and values that aid in alleviating their anxiety related to death. Various mortuary practices, characterized

by culturally diverse rituals, have gained significance in numerous societies to facilitate the deceased's transition during the death phase, mitigate grief, and instil hope in the bereaved (Gire, 2014). Nevertheless, anthropological research indicates that reactions to death differ according to the values embedded in distinct cultures (Koenig and Marshall, 2004; Davies, 2002). Evidence suggests that while death is a universal occurrence, varying cultural values lead to unique behavioural patterns and attitudes towards death and mourning (Bottum, 2007). Collective behaviours that arise in response to death are closely linked to the eschatological beliefs regarding the afterlife prevalent within the society. Supporting this perspective, Mkpa (2001) contends that the outward manifestations to commemorate an individual's death can be either solemn or celebratory, depending on the group's beliefs about death.

Around the world, burial ceremonies known as rites of passage are performed to celebrate the natural transitions experienced by all humans (Nwadiokwi *et al.*, 2016). The pioneering study by Gennep (1960) demonstrates that significant milestones such as birth, puberty, marriage, elevation to a higher social status, and death delineate an individual's life journey. Societies develop ceremonial practices to mark these transitions or to manage the confusion that arises with the onset of a new stage. However, studies reveal that among all these milestones, death is primarily associated with symbols that underscore the core values of a society (Rutherford and Carr, 1990). Almost every aspect related to death, from the way one dies to the customs surrounding burial, is shaped by cultural influences (Emke, 2002). Consequently, anthropologists during the colonial era viewed the handling of death as crucial for understanding the social frameworks and belief systems of different societies (Metcalf and Huntington, 1991). The study of death rituals within any culture goes beyond simple accounts of the methods employed for burying human remains. It entails a comprehensive examination of the social hierarchy, cosmology, and mythology of the living culture (Arriaza, 1995). Burial rites reflect the belief that human beings persist after death, and the rituals are conducted to assist the deceased in attaining their fate in the ancestral realm (Beller, 2001).

In numerous African communities, there is a prevailing belief that the peace, joy, and fulfilment of the deceased depend on the proper performance of rites. For example, Gehman (2008) asserts that a burial conducted improperly can offend ancestral spirits, potentially resulting in adverse consequences for the bereaved family. In a developing country like Nigeria, where individuals encounter various economic challenges, the societal pressure to dedicate substantial resources to honour the deceased seems to represent a misallocation of priorities. The term "funeral-induced poverty" has recently surfaced in academic discussions to underscore significant economic impacts (Orden and Hirst, 2016). Families are expected to invest considerable amounts to ensure the deceased receives a "befitting burial"; scholars contend that modern funerals have evolved into the most elaborate, expensive, and ritualised of all social events (Okaba, 1999).

The issue of households overspending on funerals in various regions has been recognised. Numerous studies revealed that in many parts of developing countries, the lack of funeral regulations leads to household debt and social unrest (Noret, 2010; La Franiere, 2011). Consequently, individuals tend to prioritise expenses related to death over the cost of living (Mkpa, 2001). This behaviour is so entrenched that people often choose to save for a funeral instead of contributing to medical expenses while an individual is still alive. This indicates that those in poverty will need to dedicate a significantly larger share of their income to funeral costs (Purcell and Cooper, 2015). When considerable resources are redirected from

productive investments to finance lavish ceremonies, researchers argue that honouring the deceased can result in the financial downfall of the living (Case *et al.*, 2014). De Witte's (2003) study demonstrates that the high costs associated with funeral practices have negatively impacted the financial well-being of grieving families. On this background, it become imperative to examine if there is any economic benefit in the burial practices among the Ibil Ogoja people in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Review of Literature

Death and Celebration of the Dead

According to Mbiti (1969), African religious traditions typically perceive death as an integral aspect of the natural cycle of life, connecting past, present, and future generations. The deceased transforms into an ancestor, a venerated entity capable of providing protection and guidance to the living, provided they are appropriately honoured. This cultural and religious importance lies at the heart of numerous African burial customs, which seek to facilitate the soul's peaceful transition and uphold harmonious relationships between the living and the deceased.

Religious convictions regarding the afterlife frequently shape how communities confront death and the subsequent rites. In various African societies, it is believed that the dead persist in a parallel spiritual realm, and their treatment in death influences their standing in the afterlife. Inadequate burial or failure to perform the necessary rites may lead to the deceased becoming a restless spirit, bringing misfortune to the family and community (Magesa, 1997). Consequently, the living bear a moral and religious duty to perform intricate rituals, including feasting, sacrifices, and prayers, to ensure that the deceased attains peace and evolves into a benevolent ancestor.

Life after death is a fundamental belief in numerous African traditional religions, influencing the manner in which funerals are performed. This belief posits that death is not the final conclusion; instead, it represents a transition to a spiritual domain where the deceased continue to exist as ancestors. In this domain, they are believed to observe, safeguard, and at times, reprimand the living, depending on how well they are remembered and honoured. As a result, African burial customs tend to be intricate and community-oriented, aimed at demonstrating respect for the deceased and ensuring their positive impact on the living.

Death signifies the conclusion of an individual's actions. This renders it impossible to examine the deceased from an anthropological perspective. Nevertheless, anthropologists investigate the behaviours of the living towards the dead and the ways in which death influences the living (Fabian, 2004). Research has shown that while various cultures have engaged with the concept of death since ancient times (Gorman and Southard, 1991), the response to the loss of an individual due to death differs because of the presence of diverse myths, legends, and interpretations regarding death and mourning across different cultures (Archer, 1999).

In numerous African societies, the passing of individuals, particularly the youth and children, is perceived as unnatural and premature, often attributed to curses, witchcraft, and magic (Lupe, 2016; Chilimampunge *et al.*, 2011). Witches are regarded as engaging in activities that do not serve the interests of humanity or society as a whole. Furthermore, death plays a significant role in reinforcing communal values. By honouring the deceased, African communities reaffirm their collective identity and shared history. The rituals associated with

death provide a moment for the community to contemplate its past, present, and future, with the memories of ancestors offering guidance and stability. As noted by Fortes and Evans-Pritchard (1940), the living are continually reminded of their responsibilities towards the deceased, thereby ensuring the preservation of cultural norms and moral values.

Economic Burden and Benefit

The economic influence of burial ceremonies on local economies within African communities is complex, involving both direct and indirect contributions. These ceremonies generally encompass a variety of services, including the sale of food and beverages, as well as the hiring of transportation and entertainment. The volume of economic activity generated by funerals, particularly for notable individuals, can be considerable. In numerous Nigerian communities, large funerals create significant economic opportunities for small enterprises. For example, the need for traditional attire and accessories during funerals offers local tailors and fabric vendors' business prospects. Likewise, food vendors, caterers, and beverage suppliers experience a marked increase in demand during funeral events, which may extend over several days (Nwosu and Anugwom, 2020). The economic impact of these activities reaches beyond the immediate community, often benefiting adjacent towns and cities.

In addition to the economic advantages, Ogundele (2015) highlights the potential of cultural tourism to safeguard and promote indigenous practices. Festivals and funerals, when showcased as cultural attractions, foster the preservation of traditional customs and provide a platform for younger generations to connect with their heritage. Nevertheless, Ogundele also cautions against the dangers of commercialisation, which may result in the commodification of cultural practices and the erosion of their original significance.

Transportation represents a sector that experiences considerable economic advantages during funerals. The necessity to move a large number of guests from various locations across the country or region to the burial site frequently results in heightened demand for local transportation services. For instance, in Cross River State, drivers and transportation firms benefit from the influx of guests attending burial ceremonies in rural areas (Okpoko, 2020). Beyond direct expenditures, burial ceremonies often generate temporary job opportunities for individuals engaged in organizing and managing the event. This encompasses roles such as security personnel, caterers, cleaners, and decorators. Consequently, the economic influence of funerals extends to the generation of both short-term and long-term employment, especially in rural regions where job prospects are scarce.

Nevertheless, it is crucial to acknowledge that while burial ceremonies bolster local economies, the substantial expenses linked to these events can also impose financial strain on families. In certain instances, families may be compelled to secure loans or liquidate assets to cover funeral costs, resulting in long-term economic difficulties (Aluko & Adebayo, 2020). This paradox underscores the dual nature of funeral expenditures in African communities—while they stimulate local economic activity, they can simultaneously impose financial challenges on families.

Traditional festivals and funerals within African communities are not simply cultural occasions; they serve as vital economic catalysts that influence local economies in numerous ways. In various African societies, these events, especially funerals, are social responsibilities that unite individuals and consequently create significant economic activity. Ranging from hospitality services to local artisans and vendors, the economic influence of traditional events is extensive, including both direct and indirect contributions to local

economies.

In nations such as Ghana and Nigeria, funerals are regarded as both cultural and economic occasions, where the financial commitments are considerable, often aimed at enhancing the social status of the deceased's family. Funerals, in particular, can evolve into community-wide events that foster business opportunities in sectors like food services, clothing, transportation, and accommodation (Obeng-Odoom, 2018). Therefore, both festivals and funerals constitute a crucial aspect of the economic framework in African communities, aiding in employment and income generation for various service providers.

Cultural events, including traditional festivals and funerals, fulfil a dual purpose in African societies: they function as instruments of social cohesion while also invigorating local economies. These occasions frequently draw large crowds, often reaching beyond the local populace to encompass visitors from distant regions. The surge of attendees for these events generates a demand for various goods and services, thereby offering economic prospects for local vendors and artisans. In Nigeria, for example, cultural festivals such as the Osun-Osogbo Festival and the Argungu Fishing Festival draw thousands of participants, including tourists, which subsequently boosts the local hospitality sector. As noted by Olayiwola and Adeleke (2019), these festivals play a crucial role in local economies by generating demand for accommodations, food, transportation, and souvenirs. Likewise, traditional funerals, particularly those for prominent individuals, attract substantial crowds, creating a ripple effect on local economic activities, including the sale of beverages, food, and ceremonial garments.

Furthermore, these events typically involve the hiring of local musicians, dancers, and drummers, which creates job opportunities and income for those engaged in the cultural sector (Nwosu et al., 2020). Additionally, local artisans benefit from the heightened demand for traditional attire, beads, and other accessories utilized during these occasions. Therefore, the cultural sector, driven by festivals and funerals, serves as an informal economic engine for numerous African communities.

In numerous African cultures, funerals serve not only to pay tribute to the deceased but also to showcase social prestige. The financial expenditures associated with funerals are frequently linked to the social status of the family of the deceased. This connection between funeral expenses and social prestige has emerged as a significant characteristic in various African societies, especially among the Yoruba, Akan, and Igbo ethnic groups. For instance, the Yoruba community in south-western Nigeria perceives elaborate funerals as a manifestation of family honour and a sign of respect for the departed. Families often make considerable efforts to ensure that the funeral is executed with splendour, even if it necessitates incurring substantial financial liabilities. Research conducted by Aluko and Adebayo (2020) reveals that Yoruba families occasionally take on debt to fund extravagant funerals, viewing this as a means to preserve or enhance their social standing. This practice generates social pressure to adhere to cultural norms, leading to extravagant expenditures on entertainment, catering, and traditional ceremonies.

In a similar vein, the Igbo people of south-eastern Nigeria have a rich history of elaborate burial rites, where the family's reputation is partially assessed based on the quality of the funeral (Onyeozili and Ebbe, 2019). The higher the financial outlay, the greater the honour believed to be conferred upon the deceased. This pursuit of social prestige through funeral spending has fostered a competitive environment, where families allocate significant amounts of money for caskets, funeral garments, and even animals for sacrifice. Although

such expenditures may impose financial strain on families, they also play a crucial role in bolstering local economies. Vendors, food providers, tailors, and musicians all gain from the demand generated by these large-scale funerals. Nevertheless, the escalating costs associated with funerals have sparked discussions within African communities regarding the sustainability of these practices and their long-term economic repercussions on families (Obeng-Odoom, 2018).

Funeral ceremonies in Nigeria have historically been a vital component of social life, carrying significant financial consequences for families and local economies. Case studies, such as Olaniyan's (2005) research, underscore the economic challenges that Nigerian families encounter as they adhere to social norms regarding funerals. Olaniyan (2005) investigated the financial responsibilities associated with Yoruba funerals, demonstrating that the wish to honour the deceased and enhance family reputation frequently results in lavish expenditures. These costs encompass the acquisition of expensive caskets, funeral clothing, transportation, catering services, and the hiring of entertainers. Olaniyan's (2005) examination of Yoruba funerals in south-western Nigeria reveals that families often resort to borrowing money or liquidating assets to meet funeral expenses, highlighting the considerable social pressure to conduct elaborate ceremonies. In certain instances, the financial strain of funerals can lead to prolonged economic difficulties for families, especially those with limited financial means. The study also notes that funeral costs can surpass the earnings of many families, driving them into poverty despite the existing communal support systems.

Moreover, Olaniyan's (2005) findings suggest that while the economic pressure on families can be substantial, funeral ceremonies simultaneously invigorate local economies. Vendors, artisans, tailors, caterers, and local enterprises gain from the heightened demand for goods and services during funerals. In Yoruba culture, where funerals are viewed as a communal event, this surge in economic activity offers temporary relief to the local economy.

Research conducted by Ezenwa (2013) offers a more comprehensive examination of how funeral celebrations influence local economies across different regions of Nigeria. Ezenwa (2013) contends that funeral ceremonies play a crucial role in enhancing the economic livelihoods of individuals engaged in the hospitality, entertainment, and artisan sectors. His research, which centers on the southeastern region of Nigeria, illustrates how these ceremonies act as platforms for economic exchanges that benefit both the bereaved family and local enterprises. Ezenwa (2013) provides case studies from communities in Igboland, where funerals frequently span several days of festivities. These occasions generate business prospects for caterers, event coordinators, tailors, and musicians. Notably, the demand for traditional funeral garments, decorations, and ceremonial items generates revenue for local artisans who focus on these goods. Furthermore, transportation services gain from the surge of visitors traveling to attend the funeral, thereby enhancing the local transport sector. Ezenwa's (2013) investigation also delves into how funeral celebrations foster social unity by redistributing wealth within the community. Relatives and friends often contribute financially to the funeral expenses, ensuring that the financial burden does not rest solely on the immediate family. This practice of communal assistance fortifies social connections and upholds the cultural principles associated with death and remembrance. Nevertheless, Ezenwa observes that the economic advantages for local businesses must be balanced against the financial pressures faced by families, especially those from lower-income backgrounds.

Cultural tourism, which encompasses the celebration of traditional festivals and funerals, has received growing recognition as a vital contributor to local economies in Africa. Festivals and funerals are perceived not merely as cultural events but also as opportunities to draw in tourists, both from within the country and abroad. Scholars like Ogundele (2015) have examined the intersection between cultural tourism and economic development in Nigeria, highlighting the potential for these events to stimulate local economies through increased spending on services such as accommodation, transportation, and entertainment.

Ogundele's (2015) work focuses on the Osun-Osogbo Festival, a prominent cultural event in Nigeria, as a case study to demonstrate the economic benefits of cultural tourism. He argues that the festival, which attracts thousands of visitors each year, creates significant economic opportunities for local businesses. Vendors selling food, drinks, souvenirs, and traditional clothing benefit from the influx of tourists, while hotels and transportation providers see increased demand for their services.

Although traditional funerals may not have the same level of visibility as large-scale cultural festivals, Ogundele (2015) suggests that they too can serve as drivers of cultural tourism, particularly when they involve elaborate ceremonies that attract attention beyond the local community. The economic effects of cultural tourism are especially pronounced in rural areas, where employment opportunities may be limited. For many local communities, cultural events provide a vital source of income, supporting livelihoods and promoting economic growth.

Theoretical Framework

Structural Functionalism

Structural Functionalism is a sociological theory that explains how social institutions, practices, and roles function together to maintain the stability and cohesion of society. This framework, originally developed by key theorists like Talcott Parsons, Bronislaw Malinowski, and A.R. Radcliffe-Brown, views society as an interconnected system where each element serves a purpose to ensure the survival and smooth functioning of the whole. When applied to burial rites, functionalism provides a lens to understand how death-related rituals help communities cope with loss, maintain social order, and reinforce cultural continuity.

At its core, structural functionalism argues that societal institutions and practices do not exist in isolation; they are interdependent and collectively contribute to the stability of society. Talcott Parsons (1951) posited that institutions like family, education, religion, and economic systems work in concert to fulfil the basic needs of society. Every role and ritual, including funeral practices, contributes to the system's stability. In the case of burial rites, this theory suggests that these rituals are not merely symbolic or religious acts but serve crucial functions in managing grief, reaffirming societal values, and maintaining the social fabric. By organizing death-related ceremonies, societies help individuals and communities navigate the emotional and social disruptions caused by death, preserving cohesion and ensuring the survival of societal norms and structures (Parsons, 1951).

Bronislaw Malinowski (1948), one of the earliest contributors to functionalist thought, emphasized the importance of cultural practices in meeting individual needs. He argued that rituals, including burial rites, play a critical role in helping individuals cope with emotional and psychological challenges such as the grief and anxiety associated with death.

In traditional African societies, including the Ibil Ogoja community of Cross River State, burial ceremonies are structured to provide emotional relief to the bereaved. These rituals often involve collective mourning, spiritual rites, and communal activities, which offer psychological comfort and allow individuals to process their loss in a culturally acceptable way. Malinowski's functionalist view suggests that the function of burial practices is not only to honor the dead but to help the living manage their grief and anxiety, thereby contributing to their emotional well-being (Malinowski, 1948). While Malinowski focused on individual needs, A.R. Radcliffe-Brown (1952) extended the functionalist approach to societal needs. He argued that rituals serve a broader social purpose by reinforcing social order, creating unity, and ensuring the continued functioning of society. According to Radcliffe-Brown, funeral rites provide a platform for reaffirming societal values, beliefs, and norms, which are essential for maintaining social cohesion in the face of death-related disruptions.

In the Ibil Ogoja community, burial practices are more than personal expressions of grief; they are social events with economic interests that reaffirm communal bonds and hierarchical structures. These ceremonies involve the participation of the entire community, with the roles of elders and leaders prominently displayed. The communal nature of these rituals helps to maintain social solidarity, as they remind the living of their interconnectedness and the importance of upholding cultural traditions. This process ensures that societal norms are preserved and that social order is maintained, even in the face of disruptive events such as death (Radcliffe-Brown, 1952). For the Ibil Ogoja people, burial rites serve as a means of reaffirming the values and beliefs that sustain their community with economic interests. The collective nature of these rites reinforces the idea that death is not merely an individual event but a communal experience that affects the entire society. Rituals, such as communal feasts, dances, and ancestral veneration, serve to reconnect the living with their cultural heritage, ensuring that societal values are passed on to future generations (Pestrucciani, 2010).

Methodology

This study employed ethnographic research design. The study was conducted in Ibil community in Ogoja Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. It is one of the autonomous communities that make up Nkum Clan. It consists of many units such as Nkporo, Ndoh, Abrumbede, Itung, Ishaya, Ngbabila, Abontek, Ishi Aleke, Mbenkpan, Moukom, Idubum, Abarutime. Ibil is located in Nkum Clan Cluster in Ogoja Local Government Area, Cross River State. It is situated at Latitude 6.5^o or 6^o30' 27 North and Longitude 8.6^o or 8^o39'36 east. IBIL is bordered in the East by the Ekajuk Clans, in the West by the Yala Tribe, in the North by Ishibori and lastly it is bordered in South by Ekajuk Ward II (Bansara) (crossrivestate.gov.ng, 2025).

Ibil people are part of the Nkum Clusters. Other groups in the Nkum Cluster include: Ishindede, Itung, Nfamju, Ikandangha, Igodor, Aladim, Ikpagada, Ukpe. The Nkum Clan originated from Ibebed, according to one Chief Emmanuel, a native of Ibil Community. They are predominantly farmers and their crops include yams, cassava, rice, beans, okro, maize, groundnuts and oil palm. The method of agriculture is not based on mechanisation because the use of crude implements still dominates the scene. Pockets of privileged individuals use machines such as tractors to cultivate their farms, mostly swamps for rice farming. Other crops being cultivated in the community do not involve the use of machines. In this light, the mode of farming here is subsistence farming. Rice, being one of the major items produced

here, is produced in enormous quantities, and the end product after harvest finds its way to Abakiliki market. The people of Ibil usually parboil their rice before taking it to the mill. Every bill or debt that accrues from the farming season is usually cleared after sales are made from farm produce. Its rice, cassava and yams are the dominant crops cultivated by both the old and young, and this forms the bulk of revenue that is generated as other crops only play complementary roles (crossrivestate.gov.ng, 2025).

The study participants selected were subjected to oral interviews from the community. The sample size determination was guided by Fusch and Creswell (2015), the criterion of saturation based on information redundancy, where sampling can be discontinued when no new information is elicited by sampling more units. The researcher was more interested in the quality of data than the number of study participants. Fatterman's (2010) big-net approach was also engaged, which describes every study participant as part of the sample size, and the total participants become the sample size of the study at the point of saturation.

Findings

Economic Benefits of Burial Ceremonies

Participants acknowledged that the social environment that characterize burial event provide conducive atmosphere for generating revenue. One of the participants in in-depth interview.

During burial events in this community, friends, relatives and guests are invited from far and near to witness the ritual practices and burial rites. Transporters in the area see increasing passengers during burial events as people move into the area to attend. People who deal on provision, snacks and restaurant businesses also see this period as their peak period. Visitors spend money to purchase locally available stuffs of their choice thereby generating revenue for the local residents (Participant P, in-depth interview, 02/04/2024).

Another participant affirmed this position, according to her:

Hawkers find the atmosphere of celebration useful for their business. Kola nuts, bitter kola, handkerchief and many other materials are sold to people. This provides a means for households to make earns meets (Participant M, in-depth interview, 02/04/2024).

Discussants during FGD recognized that burial celebrations have led to the thriving of several craft and profession and the opportunities for meaningful economic engagements in the area. One of the discussants during FGD men made the following comment:

Due to popular demand during burial celebrations in the area, hotel facilities have been built in our community to deliver service to visitors. Again, casket makers, coffin bearers, live band groups, graphic designers and fashion designers are thriving businesses in the area. Operators in these subsectors make money for themselves and also employ the youth of the area. (Discussant X FGD men, 04/04/2024).

Another participant added:

We have a lot of businessmen and women benefiting from this

burial culture economically, when someone dies, people who deal in different kinds of services will go to the family to bid for opportunities to deliver. Some relatives of the bereaved family who are into such businesses are usually contacted to bid down the price based on family ties (Participant K, in-depth interview, 04/04/2024).

Discussion of Findings

At the community level, since the death of a member of a community causes disturbance in the social order, gathering together to perform these rituals reinforces close-knit bond among residents of a community. This finding aligns with the finding of Despelder and Strickland (2011) that burial rituals strengthens social network as the community gathers to observe principles of culture, and with Peters and Bassey (20189) on causes of disturbance of social order. Similarly, the finding is in agreement with Lober *et al.*, (2006) that the symbolic actions associated with burial provides a medium for understanding and marking social change and expressing deep emotions.

It was further noted the norms of behaviour governing burial of the dead in the study area has culminated to the creation of huge investment opportunities for community members. Beyond the social psychological significance of burial ceremony, findings of the study revealed that celebration associated with burial programme has stimulated business opportunities in the area. This finding corroborates the result of a study by Abdulai (2014) that during burial events, local residents generate reasonable revenue from the provision of material and services required by visitors.

Available information from the responses of study participants revealed that there are some problems associated with the burial culture in the study area. Financial cost involved in burial ceremonies have impacted families heavily and is a cause for concern. This finding is in agreement with Stroebe *et al.*, (2008) who maintained that financial burden associated with burial ceremonies constitutes additional stress for the bereaved family.

Conclusion

The main objective of this study was to examine the economic benefits of burial practices of the burial customs of the Ibil-Ogoja people. This research examined the economic reasons behind the cultural celebration of the deceased in order to uncover what the Ibil Ogoja people stand to benefit in the celebration of the dead as a culture of the people. The study conclude from findings that burial celebrations have led to the thriving of several craft and profession and the opportunities for meaningful economic engagements in the area, and the social environment that characterize burial event provide conducive atmosphere for generating revenue.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made from the findings of the study:

1. The government should regulate ritual practices among the Ibil people in Ogoja, Cross River State
2. The elders should harmonise the burial rituals for economic benefits of the people and community in the celebration of the dead among the Ibil people in Ogoja, Cross River State.

3. The Ibil people should understand and see how to adjust to recent economic situations when it has to do with ritual for the burials of the dead.

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